

FROM PARTICLE PHYSICS TO ACCELERATORS

ABSTRACT

Philosophical essay discussing relationship between science and technology with CERN as an example.

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1. Topic

My interest in European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN) is not random. We moved to Geneva, Switzerland because of my husband's position at CERN. People always react to this fact with a question: Is he a physicist?

We have been discussing what are the driving forces behind CERN for some time. What is CERN really about? Is it its scientific research or technological development? Could it be both and if so, how are they connected? We have noticed that the answer varies depending on who you ask. Therefore, I have chosen for my assignment to examine this relationship between science and technology with CERN as an example.

2. Hypothesis

In the situational comedy *The Big Bang Theory*, the theoretical physicist Sheldon Cooper has made this cult remark to his friend Howard Wolowitz who is an aerospace engineer:

Engineering¹: Where the noble, semi-skilled laborers execute the vision of those who think and dream. Hello, Oompa Loompas of science!

Even popular culture addresses this question of the relationship between science and technology and how is it perceived in society. Although it is a television sitcom and Sheldon Cooper is a fictional character, he points out some specific questions in the philosophy of science and technology: 1) The relationship between science and technology has a strong elitist notion of technology being applied science and 2) technology (engineering) being equaled to a manual

¹ Engineering: For the sake of my assignment I will look at the engineering in a broader context of technology and treat engineering as a part of a concept of technology. Mitcham clarifies engineering to be perhaps the clearest manifestation of this phenomenon (Mitcham, 1994).

labour deprived of all knowledge. On the contrary, Eric Schatzberg in *Technology. Critical History of a Concept*, sees science as at most one factor in technology (Schatzberg, 2018, p. 1).

In this assignment I want to show that both Sheldon Cooper and Eric Schatzberg have a relevant point regarding the relationship between science and technology. I argue that this relationship has changed over the centuries and evolved to a symbiotic interdependent relationship, but the question concerning technology being an applied science has its place in this debate. I want to use CERN as an example to show this relationship. For further discussion, I include engineering in a broader definition of technology.

3. What is Science and Technology

As a start, I would like to look at the definitions of science and technology applied to the present day. Oxford Learner's Dictionary defines science and technology like this:

Science encompasses the systematic study of the structure and behavior of the physical and natural world through observation and experiment, and technology is the application of scientific knowledge for practical purposes (Oxford Learner's Dictionaries, 2020)

As this definition of technology is very narrow. It is though easily found online, and it might define the general view of our society on this matter. I would therefore like to include the definition by Einar Bøhn who sees technology having a much wider range and diverse meaning, which includes the knowledge and study of techniques, performance of those techniques, physical tools and machines that perform those techniques with us or for us (Bøhn, 2020).

At CERN, there are employed ten times more engineers and technicians than scientists. The physics programs are highly dependent on microscopic precision and require large machines using hundreds of thousands of components and devices to be able to gather the data received from the experiments. One must have the knowledge of which techniques to use to perform the

research as well as the knowledge of how to design, produce and use the technology, which exist in its instrumental view at largest only at CERN.

The definition of technology from Oxford Learner's Dictionary is very limited, pointing to technology as heavily dependent on science and supporting Sheldon Cooper's statement. It implies that technology is the application of science and focuses only on the end results-practical purposes, in other words practical application. Although the definition of science is more exhaustive, it does not say much about the experiment. An experiment is a systematic study, in other words the scientist observes a phenomenon based on a plan or methodology, then evaluates the behavior which has been observed. Certainly, one should not only observe the phenomenon, but also prove it. The experiments test a hypothesis, and the results should be possible to be measured, analyzed, evaluated, and obtained repeatedly to be able to make a conclusion. I will try to explain how the experiments at CERN are carried out in the following section.

4. Modern Technology and Big Science

The term Big Science came about in 1930s in the USA. This term referred to the large teams which needed to tackle the scientific issues as well as the magnitude of the topics. The large projects which consisted of heavy technology, large investments (usually funded by national governments) and large teams of scientists became a synonym of Big Science. Example of these are the Manhattan Project (the development of the atomic bomb during the World War II) or foundation of CERN (Dennis, 2020).

4.1 European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN)

CERN is the acronym of European Organization for Nuclear Research which was born in 1954 as a response to the need of strengthening the European scientific particle physics research after World War II. The Nazi regime had driven many European physicists to the United States. While the USA had dedicated its research in particle physics to military purposes, Europe had stagnated

and even lost most of its know-how. It was literally decimated of talents and resources. Europe, devastated by the war, was left only with a handful of scientists. But non the less they were determined to get the European science back on its feet and back on top. It was clear that no European country alone could finance and drive such extensive research. Emergence of international organizations as a response to unification of the world made good conditions for the idea of the European laboratory (CERN., 2004).

According to CERN website, CERN's mission is:

- Supply the facilities for research
- Perform the research in particle physics
- Unify the world to push the science and technology to benefit us all (www.cern.ch, 2020).

In the case of CERN, the meaning of science applies to natural science, specifically to particle physics – the study of the fundamental constituents of matter, ranging from nuclear to high-energy physics, from studies of antimatter to the possible effects of cosmic rays on clouds (CERN, 2020).

So, how does CERN perform the experiments in its scientific research? The experimental particle physics research is done in the accelerator complex, which consist of 8 accelerators-machines that accelerate particles to increasingly higher energies. An accelerator propels charged particles, such as protons or electrons, at high speeds, close to the speed of light. They are then smashed either onto a target or against other particles circulating in the opposite direction. CERN uses detectors to capture the results and collects, process, and evaluates the data with advanced computers and computer programs, not to mention that the accelerators are computer operated and controlled. This clearly shows that the performed research at CERN would be impossible without the 'megamachines' - in other words complex technology in its instrumental meaning, and without the knowledge how to make them, have the skills to make them and have the

knowledge and skills to operate them. CERN also has a strong cultural focus on the technology transfer, where technology means both the knowledge, artifacts, and usage in a broader view, for benefits of wider society. As an example, experience and knowledge of accelerators is applied in medicine, where the human-centered application of this technology (meaning knowledge and devices) is used in cancer treatment.

As we can see, some of today's definitions of technology are still limited and confirming the statement of Sheldon Cooper. Schatzberg sees two major reasons for this: 1) we take most of technology for granted and 2) the ignorance if not outright hostility toward practical arts, where knowing has been consistently ranked higher than making (Schatzberg, 2018, p. 6) (for more information see Section 5). And I would like to add one more reason and that is: not understanding the essence of technology (I will come back to this in Section 7).

5. Transition from Ancient Conception to Early Modern Science and Technology

One needs to look at the history to be able to better understand the relationship of science and technology. Before I continue, I would like to clarify that these two terms had different meanings throughout the history than what they have today. I will explain this more closely in the flow of my discourse.

Aristotle made a clear distinction between theoretical and practical understanding, where he appointed one to be higher than the other. For Aristotle, the scientific and philosophical universal understanding is essentially superior. Artists make their generalizations about subjective and individual situations and things. And because the expertise of an artist or craftsperson is individual, it is consequently inferior. Scientific knowledge or *epistémé* is known scientifically by necessity and therefore is eternal. Craft-knowledge or *techné* is concerned with production, hence a craft is the same as a state involving true reason concerned with production (Scharff & Dusek, 2014). He Aristotle became a father of the instrumental approach to *techné* or in other

words finding the best means to a specific end (Schatzberg, 2018). Although he makes a clear distinction between *epistémé* and *techné* regarding superiority, he takes in account that there is a relationship between them. In this sense *techné* does not only have the practical knowledge of how something should be made, but also the theoretical know-how (true reason). Aristotle refers to *techné* (craft) as pure practice and *epistémé* (knowledge) as pure theory. It seems like he acknowledges that to have *techné* also requires some form of knowledge. To have *techné*, does not mean only to know how to make the right product, but also why it must be done in this way (Bøhn, 2020). But even though Aristotle acknowledges that *techné* involves some type of knowledge or reasoning, it is not the same knowledge as *epistémé* (scientific knowledge) or *phronesis* (moral knowledge- how to act well). With this strict separation of *techné* from *epistémé* and *phronesis* he set the course of elitist social order for centuries to come. The established hierarchy of knowledge was strictly connected to a social order. At the top was *epistémé*, then *phronesis* and lastly *techné*. He did not just separate technical and scientific knowledge, he separated technical knowledge from any moral value and determined the hierarchy of theory over practice. And though *techné* was placed at the bottom of this hierarchy, it was not necessarily due to *techné* itself but rather due to its practice, meaning that it was the low social status of the craftsmen which determined the low position of *techné*.

In the 15th century, the economic and technical changes started to transform the relationship between *techné* and *epistémé*. A new appreciation of the mechanical arts (from Latin concept of *ars*) came into practice. Specially with inventions such as paper, gunpowder, compass and mechanical clock, artisans became more valued. Mechanical arts became more popular as in the works of Leonardo da Vinci. The works of mechanical arts helped winning the wars as well as entertaining princes, whose patronage was indispensable for both the artisans and the philosophers. Although the artisans used scientific knowledge in their creations, there was no focus on scientific approach as we know it today. It all changed towards the end of Renaissance with the Scientific Revolution.

It was an English philosopher Francis Bacon who highlighted the place and importance of modern science, but he nevertheless kept the subordination of arts to the science. Bacon tried to connect and create a bridge between science and theology, as well as between science and arts.

For in nature practical results are not only the means to improve well-being but the guarantee of truth. The rule of religion, that a man should show his faith by his works, holds good in natural philosophy too. Science also must be known by works. It is by the witness of works, rather than by logic or even observation, that truth is revealed and established (Bacon, 2014, p. 35).

Albeit science did not only explain the world, but it also helped to transform it. Hence connecting scholars with artisans but remaining the egalitarian position of science. The social order of low craftsmen and elite philosophers remained. On one side there were these elite gentlemen, on the other side were the low craftsmen. There was no interest from the elites to elevate craftsmen on the social ladder, even though craftsmen used the experimental methods and theoretical principles way before the science was acknowledged by the elites.

As Schatzberg points out: "These elite scholars did reject the categorical separation of science and material practice, but they did so without rejecting the existing hierarchy of head over hand" (2018, p.48).

So, there are two major points. First: the embracement of mechanical arts and connection between arts and science. Second: no change in a social position of the artisans practicing mechanical arts and natural philosophers practicing science. The main difference to Aristotelian philosophy and his distinction of techné and epistemé is that the techné (mechanical arts) was elevated and connected to epistemé (philosophy), but the primacy of philosophy remained and this attitude to some extent persists to a present day. This might explain Sheldon Cooper's view of engineers as being a nowadays craftsmen.

Bacon created a problem for the artisans by creating a hierarchy, where natural philosophy is on top and the progress in mechanical arts can happen only through the discoveries of natural philosophy. Although he wanted to elevate mechanical arts, at the same time he subordinated them to science and denied them any autonomous progress. He undermined Aristotle's distinction of *epistémé* and *techné*, where Aristotle separated the two but at the same time acknowledged that *techné* had knowledge although different from *epistémé*. The philosopher (a gentleman) had automatically the authority over a craftsman due to his affiliation to a higher social class. By this, both skilled technicians and their contribution such as production of fine instrumentation necessary in the experiments, lost their position and recognition. These tensions continued well into the eighteenth and nineteenth century.

6. Applied Science, Art, and Pure Science

So how should we understand applied science and where did this term come from? Francis Bacon's influence in Europe opened for new ideas concerning the relationship between science and technology throughout the age of Enlightenment. Many authors rejected the elitist position of science over technology and rather proposed the mutual dependence of the two. Applied science became an important new concept in existing concepts of science and technology, which differed from today's meanings. Art as technology included the mechanical, liberal, and fine arts, while science was viewed as knowledge in general.

In the eighteenth century, there were two directions in which the relationship between science and technology had changed. On one hand, the position of artist had been elevated by rejection of art being only instrumental, and the epistemological level of art was elevated to the level of science. Both science and technology had been viewed as divine and therefore they could not be subordinated to each other. But there had been also another change. Arts had been divided into fine arts and mechanical arts. By doing so, the status of mechanical arts was again weakened. Mechanical arts were reduced to pure craft and stripped of any creativity. This division of art and

craft made possible to elevate the social class of artists. Through their divine inspiration and creative genius, they were able to elevate themselves to middle-class status, but the artisans again were kept in the lower class.

This course of devaluation of mechanical arts continued throughout the Industrial Revolution and into the nineteenth century, where mechanical arts and industrialization according to earlier scholars was based on destruction of traditional craft skills. Even though historians changed their view on the rise of modern industry, where industrialization was based on skilled craftsmen to adapt to operation and maintenance of new machines, it did not change the fact that technology was seen as applied science. Artisans were rather seen as limitations in the progress and this could be solved only by implementation of science. Science here was viewed as the knowledge of elites implemented to manufacturing. The elevated status of art of Enlightenment was again reframed and art was seen only as the application of science. Applied science had though two main ambiguous meanings. One, it was a type of science which was suited to practical application. Two, it was a process of applying science to practical usage (technology). This ambiguity was used in the further course of history by both elites (scientists) and artisans (engineers). Scientists used applied science as application of pure science to claim credit for the innovations of the industrial age and artisans/engineers to gain credit in terms of their social status based on the concept of scientific knowledge applied to their profession and innovations.

Carl Mitcham points out that ideas associated with technology were often explained as the ideas of science used in practical context and this led to assumptions that modern technology was, and still is to some extent, applied science. According to him, this analogy hindered development of an independent philosophy of technology. He identifies theories of hydraulics, aerodynamics, information, cybernetics, and the use of mechanics in science as being technological and hence in some cases science might be described as applied technology (Mitcham, 1994, pp. 95-96) rather than technology being applied science.

7. Heidegger's and Borgmann's Take on Science and Technology

Martin Heidegger was one of the most influential German philosophers of the 20th century who introduced an important view on the concept of technology, the essence of technology and relationship between technology, science, and art. In *The Question Concerning Technology* he sees the modern physical theory of nature as an arrangement, which prepares the way for technology as well as the way for the essence of technology. He opposes that technology is neither only the means to an end nor a human activity. Although these definitions are correct; they are not all-encompassing. They do not show us what technology really is, nor what is the essence of technology. According to Heidegger the essence of technology is nothing technological, the essence of technology is the way of revealing through which the actual everywhere becomes a standing reserve (Heidegger, 2014). He does not see technology as the neutral means of our activity; he sees it as a *revealing* that sets up and challenges nature to produce energy which can be stored and transformed. Heidegger sees modern technology creating *Bestand* – the standing reserve, which allows stocking the objects that are available to be transformed, distributed, and switched. He draws up examples of a windmill and an electrical plant. The windmill runs naturally when wind is blowing and produces energy in a natural flow by nature itself, while the electric power plant ‘abuses’ the nature by transforming, unlocking and storing of energy.

According to Heidegger modern physics is the herald of *enframing* (Ge-stell). The modern physical theory of nature prepares the way for the essence of modern technology:

Enframing (Ge-stell) means the gathering together of the setting-upon that sets upon man, challenges him forth, to reveal the actual, in the mode of ordering, as standing-reserve (Heidegger, 2014, p. 311).

According to Mitcham, Heidegger means that technology is not another artifact, it is the technological attitude toward the world (Mitcham, 1994, p. 53). Heidegger does not see technology as applied science, the opposite is true, and he sees it as deceptive to see technology as applied science just because it employs the science. The essence of technology lies in its *enframing*, and physical science is the herald of *enframing*, consequently technology must employ exact science. And this is exactly the reason why modern technology might appear as applied science (Heidegger, 2014). His vision of technology agrees with Schatzberg's, where science is only one element of technology.

Heidegger further points out that modern technology is different from earlier technology because it is based on modern physics as an exact science, but also that the reverse is true: modern physics, because of its experimental approach, is dependent upon technical appliances and mechanisms and the progress in building these appliances. He sees this relationship as mutual, where science and technology work together and in consequence benefit from each other. But Heidegger also indicates that modern physics is experimental not because of the application of technological apparatus to question the nature. It is experimental because (already as the pure theory) it sets up nature to exhibit itself as a coherence of forces calculable in advance. 'It orders the experiments for the purpose of asking whether and how nature reports itself when set up in this way' (Heidegger, 2014, p. 311). And because the science as the objectification of the natural world represents the world only in mathematical terms, he suggests that instead of looking at technology as being applied science, the science should be called theoretical technology (Mitcham, 1994).

Albert Borgmann is another German philosopher specializing in the philosophy of technology, who in his work *Technology and the Character of Contemporary Life* says that science is 'both the subject and the rival of the philosophy of technology' (Borgmann, 1984, p. 15). He sees theory of technology as a theory which is trying to explain the world view and hence competing with science which is in our society looked at as a standard to accurately describe our world. He defines science in these three views: 1) science as a human and social enterprise, 2) science as

laws and theories, 3) science in its application. He explains that the first view can be seen as science being allied with or dependent on technology, the second view is the central description connected to science, the true goal of science, and the third view of science being called technology and hence being applied science.

It makes no difference to the validity of a scientific law where it has been discovered by a Jesuit or a Communist and where it is applied to kill or to cure (Borgmann, 1984, p. 17).

But at the same time, he says that it would be too simple to explain and understand our world through fitting technology in scientific view of the world merely as applied science. ‘Modern science lets the world to appear as actual in a realm of possible worlds and technology acts as a transformative force on these possibilities’ (Borgmann, 1984, p. 27). Science can explain problems based of scientific laws, but it is technology which has indefinite transformative possibilities of reality. So, as I understand it, science explains our world on a microlevel, but it is technology which can modify, replace, or supplement this world. In case of CERN, we now know more the detailed subatomic structure of things, but it is only through advanced accelerators, detectors, and computers that we were able to confirm this, and possibly thanks to more advanced technology of the future we will be able to use it to transform the world. Borgmann also agrees with Schatzberg, that scientific knowledge is an important condition of technology, but it is not sufficient and there is more to technology than scientific knowledge.

So how is CERN really setting up nature to reveal itself in terms of science and technology. Not that CERN is setting up the nature only on Earth, CERN is setting up the nature even outside of the realm of Earth. Creation of antimatter and search for dark matter is some of CERN’s Ge-stell (enframing). Antimatter is very expensive to create at this moment and it annihilates right away when it meets matter. To be able to explore, contain and store it, in other words to enframe it, meaning to set it up (create it), reveal it (detect it and study it), and store it as a standing reserve (contain it for further utilisation) - is CERN’s essence of technology, which will transform the

world as we know it. Both Heidegger and Borgmann were right that we are setting up the nature to reveal itself as a standing reserve, and it is indeed the technology that has transformative possibilities of the world regarding CERN's scientific questions. It is technology and its limits which now define and at the same time constrain the science. At CERN, the scientific research does not explain what we knew before naturally, pre-scientifically. CERN is trying to find the answers on fundamental questions what the universe is made of, and it is done through and limited by technology.

8. Relational Model of Science and Technology at CERN

Finally, I would like to connect philosophical views of this complex relationship between science and technology to case of CERN. The success of the Manhattan Project in terms of the creation of the atomic bomb and the enormous credit given to physics for the success of the Allied forces winning the war led to an increased support for basic research. Basic research characterized as pure science or fundamental science distorted again the role of technology. Science had no concern for practical utility and many scientists were defending the autonomy of science (Schatzberg, 2018). This environment created positive circumstances for foundation of CERN with focus on fundamental particle physics. And even though the importance of science has played a major role; it would not be possible without advanced technology. Throughout the decades of its existence, the focus on pure fundamental science has evolved and today's CERN recognizes advancing in science, technology, and knowledge transfer as CERN's core values.

Fabjan et al. explains it very clearly by saying that basic research of CERN implies large costs to the member states, which is normally accepted in the long run, if there are other benefits to the society. Technology developed at CERN has found many uses in different industries worldwide. Accelerator applications encompass treating cancer, welding, improving material qualities and much more. When existing technologies are obsolete or inadequate, they trigger new developments and new spheres of usage (Fabjan C. W., Taylor, Treille, & Wenninger, 2017).

Figure 1 CERN's Science and Technology Relational Atomic Model

According to my model, the relationship of science and technology at CERN must be seen in a broader sense. Not only they are interdependent, rather symbiotic, and overlapping, they have also a tight relationship and interdependency with society and morals. Not to mention that politics and economics influence the further direction and development of both science and technology of CERN even though some level of independence and self-regulation is reserved to CERN itself. To put it simply, no member state would become a member of CERN if there was no pay-off for the society and no member state would pay contributions to pure scientific research if there was no technological development or possible technological application of such

research in a wider context. This also explains the focus on knowledge transfer, which is technological in terms of knowledge and instruments. It is socially influenced with a strong focus on moral values. Morals play an important role in what industries and in which direction CERN technology is implemented.

Although CERN's science is dedicated to answer fundamental questions, the wider use of such research is inevitable. CERN contributes immensely to new technology in form of knowledge as well as technological implications. In parallel, CERN is dependent on technological devices, machinery, technological apparatus, and its innovations. One of its main goals is to transfer technological knowledge to the broader public and other industries. At CERN, the technology does not only refer to material things, but it also refers to ideas, techniques, and knowledge, which according to CERN's main mission should benefit society. CERN's technology is rather the driving horse of CERN's science than its servant.

9. Conclusion

The relationship between science and technology is very complex and there is not one simple definition or answer. There are multiple reasons for it, which I hope I have been able to clarify showcase on the example of CERN. I believe CERN as of 2020 has overcome the unbalanced relationship between science and technology from previous centuries, which is clearly expressed through CERN's activities and its mission. If there is still any biased understanding of science being elevated over technology, it is merely based on the individual attitude rather than realistic view of this relationship. I believe Schatzberg is right about science being only a part of technology and CERN is a clear proof of this.

According to Fabjan et al. the value of CERN as the host laboratory for worldwide collaborations of scientists and engineers extends far beyond basic research. CERN and the collaborating universities and institutions are together enhancing their efforts in knowledge transfer and education, triggering innovation and communicating the role of basic research as a motor for

new technologies of relevance to society (Fabjan C. , Taylor, Treille, & Wenninger, 2017). The latter being true in reverse as well. The role of technology as a motor for new science is just as important if not crucial.

I would like to end my assignment with the words of Francis Bacon, which are as true today as they were then:

In fact the divorce between the two activities, speculation and experiment, has always obtained. But if the two could be joined in a closer and holier union the prospects of a numerous and happy issue are bright indeed (Bacon, 2014, p. 36).

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